

Manuscript Number:

Title: Evaluation of the coupling of multi-effect distillation plants to concentrating solar power plants

Article Type: Full Length Article

Keywords: solar energy; concentrated solar power; thermodynamic simulation; cogeneration; desalination; power plant cooling

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Abstract: The aim of this work is to analyze whether the integration of Multi-Effect Distillation (MED) process into a Concentrating Solar Power (CSP) plants can be more competitive, under certain conditions, than the independent freshwater and power production by connecting a Reverse Osmosis (RO) system to a CSP plant. For this purpose, different CSP+MED configurations using the steam from the turbine as the energy source of the desalination process have been evaluated and compared to the simple combination of a CSP plant connected to a RO plant. A sensitivity analysis has been carried out varying different parameters of the whole system (the specific electric consumption and the exhaust vapor temperature) and calculating in each case the overall thermodynamic efficiency of the combined system for the same net production of electricity and desalinated water. This analysis has been performed for the three types of refrigeration methods usually employed in power plants (dry cooling, once-through and evaporative water cooling) and the results have been discussed in detail.

Almería 30 July 2014

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Energy Journal

Dear Editor,

Please consider the following paper for publication in Energy journal.

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“Evaluation of the coupling of multi-effect distillation plants to concentrating solar power plants”

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Patricia Palenzuela, Guillermo Zaragoza, Diego C. Alarcón-Padilla, Julián Blanco.

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This paper helps to choose the best concepts of the coupling of MED plants to CSP plants with respect the independent freshwater and power production by connecting a Reverse Osmosis (RO) system to a CSP plant.

We will appreciate helpful comments and recommendations by the Editor-in-Chief and the reviewers.

Yours sincerely

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Evaluation of the coupling of multi-effect distillation plants to concentrating solar power plants

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Abstract

The aim of this work is to analyze whether the integration of Multi-Effect Distillation (MED) process into a Concentrating Solar Power (CSP) plants can be more competitive, under certain conditions, than the independent freshwater and power production by connecting a Reverse Osmosis (RO) system to a CSP plant. For this purpose, different CSP+MED configurations using the steam from the turbine as the energy source of the desalination process have been evaluated and compared to the simple combination of a CSP plant connected to a RO plant. A sensitivity analysis has been carried out varying different parameters of the whole system (the specific electric consumption and the exhaust vapor temperature) and calculating in each case the overall thermodynamic efficiency of the combined system for the same net production of electricity and desalinated water. This analysis has been performed for the three types of refrigeration methods usually employed in power plants (dry cooling, once-through and evaporative water cooling) and the results have been discussed in detail.

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1. Introduction

Seawater desalination processes are intensive energy consumers, which makes water scarcity problems even worse in the context of the energy crisis and the need to reduce consumption of fossil fuels. On the other hand, advantage can be taken from the typical geographical coincidence of water shortage and high solar radiation. This is the case of the Mediterranean area and the MENA region, which are increasingly suffering from a serious lack of fresh water supplies. They are good candidates for the deployment of concentrating solar power (CSP) plants due to the high values of solar direct normal irradiance (DNI) available. The cogeneration of electricity and fresh water using concentrating solar thermal technologies (CSP+D) is proposed to solve both power and water problems while reducing the cost of combined power and desalination production against independent plants. In addition, the cost-effectiveness of the cogeneration plant is also expected to improve by making better use of a common infrastructure and the economy of scale of the steam turbine. Another advantage is the considerable additional savings of greenhouse gas emissions coming from the production of fresh water, since the majority of desalination plants are currently fed by fossil energy sources.

In the context of the integration of water desalination technologies in CSP plants, reverse osmosis (RO) and multi-effect distillation (MED) have been preselected as the

1 most promising technologies for the coupling to solar power plants [1]. In the case of
2 low temperature MED (LT-MED), the steam leaving the turbine is used as the thermal
3 energy source in the desalination process. This means that the desalination plant must
4 be very close to the turbine, since the low-pressure exhaust steam has very high specific
5 volume and pipes with very large diameters are needed to conduct it to the desalination
6 plant. In the case of RO, the energy needed to feed the high pressure pump comes from
7 the electricity produced by the CSP plant, and both plants can be located in different
8 places. The choice of one or other desalination system depends on many factors, such as
9 the required power to water ratio, cost of fuel energy charged to the desalting process,
10 electricity sales, capital costs, and local requirements [2]. Besides all the potential
11 benefits of combining power and water production, the integration of desalination into
12 CSP plants is not yet a straightforward issue and many technological aspects remain to
13 be discussed. The main one is the definition of the best concepts and schemes of the
14 integration. Another sensitive issue is the land cost and availability in the case of the
15 CSP plant being located near the sea due to the desalination demands. Solar DNI is
16 normally lower in these areas, which makes CSP plants most optimal locations to be
17 separated from the coast. Finally, the transient behaviour of solar energy is a problem
18 for desalination plants as they require constant operation, even when they work at
19 partial load. To solve all of these issues, a thermo-economic analysis that considers
20 these and other matters is needed to select the best option to produce water and
21 electricity.
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27 Despite the fact that there are no real CSP+D plants built yet, several studies related to
28 the integration of both technologies have been published. Trieb et al. [3,4] and Trieb
29 and Müller-Steinhagen [5] investigated the potential for combining solar power and
30 desalination for the Mediterranean and MENA regions. They concluded that seawater
31 desalination based on concentrating solar power offers affordable, sustainable and
32 secure freshwater potentials that are large enough to cope with the growing deficits in
33 the Mediterranean and MENA regions. Other works have proved the potential of
34 CSP+D in specific locations: Gaza strip [6], New Mexico [7], Oman [8], SE Spain [9]
35 and Abu Dhabi [10]. Economic studies have also been reported. Olwig et al. [11]
36 performed a techno-economic study for the combination of parabolic trough power
37 plants for electricity and water production with MED and ultrafiltration/RO plants in
38 two specific locations of Israel (Ashdod) and Jordan (Aqaba). Both integrated systems
39 used a wet cooling system and the same fresh water and electricity production were
40 taken into account. The results showed that the configuration with RO had economic
41 benefits in comparison to CSP+MED configuration except for very high electricity
42 prices. Moser et al. [12] carried out another techno-economic study for water desalination
43 and CSP plants in different MENA countries considering a dry cooling system for the
44 turbine. For each location, four configurations were analyzed, combining two types of
45 solar technologies (parabolic trough and linear Fresnel reflector) and two types of
46 desalination processes: LT-MED and RO. The main result was that in most of the cases
47 studied the solar field required for the CSP+RO was larger than for the CSP+LT-MED,
48 due to the higher electrical consumption of the RO overcompensating the lower thermal
49 efficiency of the turbine in the MED case. In addition, hybrid desalination systems have
50 been analyzed in combination with power plants. A thermal and environmental analysis
51 for two CSP+D schemes was published by Alrobaei [13]. The first configuration
52 consisted of a CSP plant using parabolic-trough collectors, coupled with a RO/LT-MED
53 hybrid system. The second one was the same cogeneration plant but integrating a gas
54 turbine unit, which increased the power production in the steam turbine by using waste
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1 heat to generate additional vapor. The results showed that the latter scheme seemed the
2 most effective in terms of technical, economical and environmental sustainability.

3 Other works have focused on modelling and optimization of CSP+D plants. Schmitz et
4 al. [14] proposed an analysis with tailor-made simulation models for parabolic trough
5 solar power plants in combination with MED and RO, using the seawater properties of
6 the Gulf of Almería (in the Mediterranean Sea) for the performance simulation of the
7 desalination plants. It was concluded that RO was the most suitable technology for
8 seawater desalination in combination with parabolic trough solar power plants.

9 Ghobeity et al. [15] developed system-level models in order to optimize the operation of
10 a cogeneration solar-thermal plant in Cyprus. The solar thermal power plant (4 MW_e)
11 was based on a regenerative Rankine steam cycle with an extraction turbine and the
12 desalination systems used were RO and MED. The results showed that, the extraction of
13 steam at low pressure yielded the highest income. Also, it was shown that for a small-
14 scale MED (suitable for the power considered), the energetic requirements were much
15 higher than for a typical RO plant.
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20 A very important issue to take into account in CSP plants is the choice of the most
21 suitable cooling system. The condensation of the exhaust steam from the turbine can be
22 made with dry or wet cooling. Wet cooling for thermoelectric power plants is
23 accomplished using two methods: once-through cooling and evaporative water cooling.
24 Once-through cooling uses large volumes of water (usually seawater and in quantities in
25 the order of 90000-100000 m³/MWh). This produces an environmental impact by
26 returning at a higher temperature and can be a limiting factor if the water source is not
27 refreshed enough. On the other hand, evaporative water cooling requires a constant
28 supply of freshwater, as it consumes most of the water directly through evaporation.
29 This is the most used cooling method in CSP, cogeneration and combined cycle plants.
30 However, if evaporative water cooling continues to be utilized in new power plants,
31 consumptive water use for electricity production could be more than double by 2030
32 [16]. Moreover, for sites that have a limited supply of water the use of dry air cooling to
33 condense the exhaust steam of the turbine is more suitable, since it reduces the water
34 consumption of the CSP plant to about 0.30-0.34 m³/MWh [17]. Several works have
35 been made in order to evaluate and compare the existing refrigeration modes of a power
36 plant. The authors of this paper carried out the evaluation of wet (evaporative water and
37 once-through) and dry cooling technologies of different CSP+D configurations (with
38 MED and RO desalination plants) in the Mediterranean area [17]. It was obtained that
39 the CSP+RO combination was the most favourable and the use of evaporative water
40 cooling was the most efficient and economical in terms of the electricity production.
41 However, the cost of water was higher than for the once-through and dry cooling
42 systems. Also, two different cooling technologies for a power cycle of 50 MW_e solar
43 thermal power plant were compared from an exergetic point of view [18]. The first
44 design configuration used a cooling tower while the second configuration used an air
45 cooled condenser. It was concluded that, from an exergetic point of view, the use of an
46 air cooled condenser was not an efficient solution for working at low exit turbine
47 pressures, which is the case of the Mediterranean area. However, it became more
48 competitive at the higher pressures corresponding to much warmer regions. On the other
49 hand, Richter et al. [19] studied different combinations of dry and wet cooling systems
50 using a simulation tool for the comparative analysis. It was concluded that the use of
51 hybrid wet/dry cooling reduced the energy cost penalty to below that of air cooling
52 alone and saved about 80% of the water compared to a water-cooled plant.
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1 In none of the previous papers published, a thermodynamic assessment was carried out
2 to select the most suitable CSP+D cogeneration plant and refrigeration system of the
3 power cycle, considering different locations in which the installation of CSP+D plants
4 could arise, which is what we propose in this work. This paper presents a sensitivity
5 analysis for the coupling of several desalination technologies into parabolic trough CSP
6 (PT-CSP) plants. The first three configurations implement different concepts of Multi-
7 effect Distillation (MED) plants: a Low-Temperature Multi-effect Distillation (LT-
8 MED) plant directly integrated into the power cycle or after thermal vapor compression
9 of the low pressure steam coming from the turbine, and a typical Thermal Vapor
10 Compression Multi-effect Distillation (TVC-MED) scheme with low pressure steam
11 recovered from the distillation unit. The reference configuration consists of a Reverse
12 Osmosis (RO) plant connected to a PT-CSP plant. The variables evaluated were the
13 specific electric consumption of the desalination plants and the exhaust steam
14 temperature. In all the configurations, the same values of net power and fresh water
15 production were established as input parameters and the analysis was carried out for
16 three different cooling technologies: once-trough, evaporative water cooling and dry air
17 cooling, except for the case in which a LT-MED unit replaces the condenser in the PT-
18 CSP plant. The study was performed for different boundaries conditions in order to
19 evaluate in which cases the configurations PT-CSP+MED are more efficient than the
20 configuration PT-CSP+RO.
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26 **2. Description of the systems**

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29 The different CSP+D configurations under consideration were:

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31 - LT-MED unit integrated into a PT-CSP plant using all the exhaust steam from
32 the turbine, therefore replacing the condenser (Configuration #1).
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34 - LT-MED unit integrated into a PT-CSP plant after vapor compression, using
35 part of the exhaust steam combined with higher pressure steam extracted in a
36 previous step from the turbine, which we named LT-MED+TVC, (Configuration
37 #2).
- 38
39 - TVC-MED unit integrated into a PT-CSP plant using motive steam from the
40 turbine (Configuration #3).
- 41
42 - RO unit connected to a PT-CSP plant (Configuration #4).

43 *2.1 Configuration #1*

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46 The integration of a LT-MED unit into a PT-CSP plant is proposed in this configuration
47 by replacing the conventional cooling subsystem of the power cycle. Therefore, the
48 thermal energy that would be dissipated in the condenser is used to produce fresh water,
49 which is an extra value for the combined system. However, in this case, the exhaust
50 steam must leave the turbine at a slightly higher pressure than in the rest of
51 configurations analyzed, since it must feed the LT-MED desalination plant at 70 °C.
52 This imposes a penalty in the power production and therefore a lower efficiency.
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56 Process flow diagram for this configuration is shown in Fig. 1. This scheme is based on
57 the typical configuration of current commercial CSP plants based on parabolic trough
58 collectors. In this case, four extractions are taken from the low pressure turbine (ST2)
59 instead of the typical five that are made when the steam is left to expand completely
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(configurations #2 to #4). The steam leaving the turbine ST2 (point 11) is condensed in the first effect of the LT-MED unit, then is mixed with the condensate from the feedwater heater 4 (FWH4) in the mixing chamber and the resulting condensed steam (feedwater) is pumped back into the power conversion system.

2.2 Configuration #2

In this case, as opposed to the previous one, the cooling system of the PT-CSP plant is not fully replaced by the LT-MED and the exhaust steam of the turbine ST2 is left to expand completely. Instead, the LT-MED plant is powered by the thermal energy coming from a thermal vapor compressor (LT-MED+TVC) which uses part of the exhaust steam as entrained vapor and high-pressure steam extracted from the own turbine as motive steam in the ejector. This also results in a decrease of the overall efficiency of the power production. The remaining exhaust steam is condensed through the condenser of the power cycle. This is a very interesting combination since in this case, unlike the previous one, the desalination process does not have to follow the load of the power cycle due to the existence of the condenser in the PT-CSP plant. Another advantage of this configuration is that the condensation of the exhaust steam does not require the operation of the desalination plant, which could be a limitation when the desalination plant fails.

A process flow diagram for this configuration is shown in Fig. 2. The ejector is fed by steam from one of the extractions of the low pressure turbine (point 8) as motive steam and by part of the exhaust steam from the power cycle as entrained vapor (point 10). The intermediate pressure vapor (named compressed vapor) resulting from the ejector (point 11) is used as the thermal energy source in the LT-MED plant producing fresh water (point 13). The remaining exhaust steam is condensed through the condenser of the power cycle. The condensate that leaves the condenser is mixed with the condensate that leaves the MED plant first effect and with the condensate from the FWH5. The condensate from the mixing chamber (point 14) continues the process within the power cycle.

2.3 Configuration #3

This configuration has the same advantages as the previous one, since the exhaust steam from the turbine is also fully expanded, condensing through the cooling system of the PT-CSP plant. In this case, a TVC-MED is integrated into the PT-CSP plant using high pressure steam from the turbine to feed the steam ejector coupled to the MED plant. As in the previous configuration, the required high pressure extraction results in a decrease of the overall efficiency of the power production. However, TVC-MED plants have higher Gain Output Ratio (*GOR*) than LT-MED plants, that is, lower thermal energy is required to produce the same amount of fresh water as part of the vapor that is generated in one of the effects of the MED plant is recovered. Moreover, the cooling requirements of TVC-MED units are lower than those ones for LT-MED units, since part of the vapor generated in the process is extracted to be used as entrained vapor in the ejector, so a lower amount of cooling water is required in the MED final condenser.

Fig. 3 shows a process flow diagram for this configuration. The steam ejector uses part of the steam extracted from the low pressure turbine (ST2) as the motive steam (point 8), and steam from an intermediate effect of the desalination plant is used as entrained

1 vapor (point 12). The resulting compressed vapor (point 11) is used as the thermal
2 energy source in the TVC-MED plant to produce fresh water (point 13). The condensed
3 steam leaving the TVC-MED first heat exchanger is mixed with the condensate from
4 the condenser of the PT-CSP plant and the condensate from the FWH5. The mixture of
5 condensates leaves the mixing chamber (Point 14) and is pumped to the rest of
6 feedwater heaters to continue the cycle.
7

8 *2.4 Configuration #4*

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10 This configuration corresponds to the basic combination of a RO desalination system
11 with a PT-CSP plant. It has the advantage that the desalination process is completely
12 independent from the power generation and can be even separated geographically. In
13 this case, there are no penalties in the power production since there are no modifications
14 to the power cycle. However, the cooling requirements are higher than the previous
15 cases since all the exhaust steam from the turbine must be condensed.
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19 In Fig. 4 a process flow diagram is shown for this configuration. As it can be seen, part
20 of the power output from the PT-CSP plant is used to feed the high pressure pump,
21 which pressurizes the seawater to the membranes to produce fresh water (point 13).
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24 **3. Sensitivity analysis**

25 *3.1 Simulation and modelling*

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27 For the thermodynamic analysis of the dual cycles to produce fresh water and
28 electricity, a model was developed and implemented within Engineering Equation
29 Solver software environment [20]. A set of nonlinear, algebraic equations were
30 generated to characterize the thermodynamic cycle in each case. All the components
31 associated with the power cycle (pump, reheater, feedwater heaters, valves, heat
32 exchanger, condenser and turbine) were analyzed by steady-flow energy and mass
33 transfer equations. Table 1 shows the operating conditions used as input variables of the
34 model for the thermodynamic simulation, which were taken from the power cycle of the
35 commercial plant Andasol-1 in Spain [18].
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41 The cogeneration cycle was modelled assuming that all the components, except the
42 steam ejector, are adiabatic. Changes in potential and kinetic energy of fluid streams
43 were assumed negligible, as changes in fluid state between the outlet and the inlet of
44 each component. Pressure losses in the steam lines of the low and high pressure FWH
45 were set to 0.1 bar, and in the feedwater lines of the low and high FWH to 0.1 bar and
46 0.5 bar, respectively. Also, pressure losses in the steam generation system and in the
47 reheater were set to 2 bars. A terminal temperature difference (which is the difference
48 between the saturation temperature corresponding to the steam inlet pressure and the
49 feedwater outlet temperature) and a drain cooler approach (which is the difference
50 between drain outlet temperature and feedwater inlet temperature) of 4 °C and 5 °C,
51 respectively, were considered in the FWH. Isentropic efficiencies of 85.2 % and 85 %
52 were set for the high and low pressure turbines, respectively, and of 75 % for the pumps
53 of the cycle. In addition, the following assumptions were made: condensed steam exited
54 the condenser as saturated liquid ($x=0$) and no pressure losses were set through it; steam
55 was extracted from an intermediate point of the TVC-MED plant as saturated vapor
56 ($x=1$); compressed steam from the ejector entered the TVC-MED and LT-MED+TVC
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1 plants as saturated vapor ($x=1$) after passing through a temper to obtain the vapor at the
2 equilibrium temperature corresponding to the pressure required in the first effect;
3 condensed steam left the first effect of the MED plants as saturated liquid ($x=0$);
4 feedwater exited the deaerator as saturated liquid ($x=0$); the condensate mixture left the
5 mixing chamber as saturated liquid ($x=0$).
6

7 The simulation results for each configuration provide: (i) the vapor mass flow rates that
8 flow in the ST1 and ST2 turbines and those that are extracted from them; (ii) the motive
9 and entrained vapor mass flow rates in the steam ejectors; (iii) the condensate mass flow
10 rates flowing through the feedwater heaters and the mixing chambers; (iv) the enthalpy
11 of all the streams of the power cycle; (v) the pressure and temperature of the streams
12 whose values are not given in the model. Moreover, the model provides the gross power
13 produced by the turbines, the net output thermal capacity required by the dual cycle and
14 its thermal efficiency. The net power of the PT-CSP plant was considered in all
15 configurations to be 50 MW_e , which is the normal size of a commercial PT-CSP plant
16 [21]. Also, 24 h operation of the desalination plant was considered, which is especially
17 important in the case of MED plants from an operational point of view. In all the
18 configurations proposed, except in the case of PT-CSP+LT-MED in which the
19 condenser of the power cycle is not required, the sensitivity analysis was carried out for
20 the three cooling technologies: dry cooling, once-through and evaporative water
21 cooling. On the other hand, the condensation of the vapor generated in the last effect of
22 the MED plants was considered to be carried out by once-through cooling.
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28 The gross power production of the CSP+D plants is higher than the net one due to the
29 power consumed by the pumps, by the desalination plants and by the cooling systems.
30 In the case of the cooling systems, the following considerations were taken into account
31 to solve the model:
32

- 33 • In the case of dry cooling, one part of the gross electricity production was used
34 to drive the air condensers. The assessment of such consumption was carried
35 out considering a penalty of 5 % in the electricity produced annually [19].
- 36 • In the case of once-through cooling, one part of the gross electricity produced
37 was consumed by the pump that circulates the water from the sea through the
38 condenser, which resulted in a value of 0.25 kWh/m^3 . Moreover, specific
39 seawater flow rate of $87.08 \text{ m}^3/\text{MW}_e\text{h}$ was taken into account to condense the
40 exhaust vapor from the turbine [22].
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45 In all the desalination plants analysed, the same net fresh water production (Point 13) as
46 that one obtained in Configuration #1 was considered, since in this configuration all the
47 exhaust steam coming from ST2 is used to drive the desalination plant. For this purpose,
48 a model of a LT-MED plant developed by the authors [23] was integrated into the
49 power plant model. Two LT-MED plants with different number of effects were
50 analyzed: a 14-effect LT-MED plant and a 12-effect LT-MED plant. The number of
51 effects was set according to the seawater temperature of the location of interest. The
52 higher the seawater temperature of the location, the higher the last effect's vapor
53 temperature of the MED plant is and therefore the lower its number of effects is.
54 As the seawater temperature in the South of Europe is about $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, the 14-effect MED
55 plant was chosen for this region considering a last effect's vapor temperature of the
56 MED plant of $35 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. In the case of MENA region, the seawater temperature is around
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30 °C which means a last effect's vapor temperature of the MED plant of 40 °C and therefore the 12-effect LT-MED has been considered for this region.

Notice that the net fresh water production is slightly lower than the gross one, since a part of the water produced is consumed internally in the power plant for solar collectors mirror cleaning. Also, in the case of evaporative cooling, an additional amount of water must be produced to be used in the evaporative tower. In all the study cases, the specific water consumption for cleaning the mirrors was considered 0.07 m³/MWh_e [22]). In the case of evaporative water cooling, a specific fresh water flow rate of 3 m³/MWh was established [22].

In addition to the fresh water production, the *GOR* (defined as the mass of distillate produced for every mass unit of steam supplied to the desalination unit) was obtained from the computational simulation of this configuration. The same value was used in Configuration #2 and a *GOR* 20 % higher was considered for the TVC-MED plant [24] in Configuration #3.

For these two last configurations, a semi-empirical model developed by El-Dessouky [25] was used for the calculation of the steam ejector mass flow rates (both motive and entrained vapor flow rates). Notice that the entrained vapor for the TVC in Configuration #3 was taken from the effect 8 in the case of the plant of 12-effects and the effect 5 for the 14-effects plant. Two important parameters that characterize the steam ejectors are the compression and entrained ratio (*Cr* and *Ra*, respectively). In Configuration #3, the compression ratio, *Cr* (the pressure ratio of the compressed and entrained vapors) was kept constant at a value of 1.7. In Configuration #2, it varied as a function of the entrained vapor pressure according to the exhaust steam temperature (see Table 1). In this case, *Cr* ranged between 1.8 (for an exhaust steam temperature of 57 °C) and 5.0 (for an exhaust steam temperature of 37 °C). The entrainment ratio, *Ra* (the mass flow rate ratio of the motive and entrained ratio) was constant at a value of 1.4 for Configuration #3, and varied in a range of 1.5 (for an exhaust steam temperature of 57 °C) and 4.2 (for an exhaust steam temperature of 37 °C) for Configuration #2.

3.2 Evaluation of the overall efficiency

The sensitivity analysis was carried out by the assessment of the overall efficiency of the PT-CSP+D system obtained from computational simulation using the model of each configuration. This efficiency was defined by:

$$\eta_{th} = \frac{\dot{W}_{net}}{m_1 \cdot (h_1 - h_{16}) + m_3 \cdot (h_4 - h_3)} \quad (1)$$

where \dot{W}_{net} is the gross power production in the turbines minus the power required by the pumps, the desalination plant and the cooling system; \dot{m}_1 the vapor mass flow rate that enters ST1 turbine; h_1 the specific enthalpy of this vapor; h_{16} the specific enthalpy of the feedwater that enters the pre-heater of the vapor system generator (composed of pre-heater, evaporator and superheater); \dot{m}_3 the vapor mass flow rate entering the re-heater; and h_4 the specific enthalpy of the vapor leaving the re-heater.

1 The sensitivity analysis was performed varying different parameters of the system. On
2 one hand, the specific electric consumption (*SEC*) of the LT-MED plant was varied in a
3 range of 1.4-2.4 kWh/m³. This is equivalent to assuming a given nominal value but
4 adding the pumping of seawater from the sea to the desalination plant. In the case of the
5 TVC-MED plant, the specific electric consumption ranged between 1.2-2.2 kWh/m³,
6 since the nominal value for this desalination plant is lower as mentioned before. On the
7 other hand, the *SEC* of the RO was varied in a range of 3.5-5.5 kWh/m³, which reflects
8 the maximum value of 5.5 kWh/m³ for plants without improvements and the minimum
9 value of 3.5 kWh/m³ considering energy recovery devices. Concerning the steam
10 temperature at the outlet of the turbine (Point 10 in the diagrams), a set of different
11 temperatures were considered: 37 °C, 42 °C, 47 °C, 52 °C and 57 °C; covering a wide
12 range of conditions that match the three refrigeration systems considered.
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16 The condensing temperature in the refrigeration system is related to the exhaust steam
17 conditions and to the ambient conditions of the location selected. In the case of dry
18 cooling, the minimum attainable temperature is the dry bulb temperature, so places with
19 low ambient temperatures such as that ones in the South of Europe require low steam
20 temperature at the outlet of the turbine. Therefore, exhaust steam temperatures ranging
21 from 37°C to 47°C will be considered for this region, and those ones between 52°C and
22 57°C will be considered for MENA region. In the case of evaporative water cooling, the
23 minimum attainable temperature is the wet bulb temperature that depends on the dry
24 bulb temperature and the relative humidity of the location. Thus, low exhaust steam
25 temperatures (between 37°C and 47°C) are more suitable for places in the South of
26 Europe (with low values of the wet bulb temperature) and high exhaust steam
27 temperature (between 52°C and 57°C) are usual in places within MENA region (with
28 high values of relative humidity and dry bulb temperature).
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32 **4. Results and discussion**

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35 From the computational simulations of Configuration #1 for each region, the *GOR* and
36 the net fresh water production were obtained. With regards to the *GOR*, the following
37 values were achieved: 8.4 for the 12-effects LT-MED plant in the case of MENA
38 region, and 10 for the 14-effects LT-MED plant in the case of the South of Europe. The
39 resulting net fresh water production varied as a function of the *SEC* considered. The
40 larger the LT-MED *SEC*, the larger the gross power of the turbine, which means more
41 exhaust steam leaving the turbine and therefore more fresh water obtained from the LT-
42 MED plant. The resulting values ranged between 34305-35318 m³/day for the 12-
43 effects LT-MED and between 41094-42554 m³/day for the 14-effects LT-MED plant.
44 Then, in each case, the overall efficiency of the dual power and fresh water cycle was
45 obtained for each value of fresh water production, each value of *SEC* and each
46 refrigeration system considered (only in the cases of Configurations #2 to #4).
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51 Tables 2-11 show some of the results obtained from comparing the cogeneration
52 systems involving thermal desalination with the one including reverse osmosis, in terms
53 of the overall efficiency for different values of the *SEC* of the desalination system. The
54 effects of evaporative and once through cooling on the overall efficiency of the power
55 cycle are similar. Therefore, only the case of evaporative water cooling has been shown
56 since it is the most used system in CSP. In all the comparisons, shaded values indicate
57 the cases where the overall efficiency of the PT-CSP+MED system is larger than the
58 PT-CSP+RO system. The first two tables (Tables 2 and 3) correspond to the comparison
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1 of Configuration #1 and #4, considering dry cooling in the PT-CSP+RO case. Table 2
2 show that in the South of Europe region, the configuration with LT-MED is more
3 efficient thermodynamically than the one with RO from a value of the RO *SEC* of 5
4 kWh/m³ upwards for all the *SEC* LT-MED studied. On the other hand, the results
5 depicted in Table 3 show that in MENA region Configuration #1 is more efficient than
6 Configuration #4 regardless the *SEC* of the RO unit.
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8 Tables 4 and 5 show the same comparison for the case of evaporative water cooling in
9 the condenser of the PT-CSP+RO system. Due to the fact that the electric consumption
10 required in this condenser is lower, the PT-CSP+RO is more competitive than the PT-
11 CSP+LT-MED for a higher number of cases than in the previous comparison. The
12 results obtained in Table 4 show that in the South of Europe the configuration with RO
13 is more efficient than the configuration with LT-MED for all the cases considered,
14 except for the case of lowest *SEC* LT-MED and highest *SEC* RO. On the other hand, in
15 MENA region, the PT-CSP+LT-MED system is more efficient from a value of RO *SEC*
16 of 4 kWh/m³ upwards (see Table 5).
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20 However, when integrating a LT-MED unit into a CSP plant, Configuration #1 might be
21 non-practical for the reasons explained in section 2. The other two MED configurations
22 (PT-CSP+LT-MED+TVC and PT-CSP+TVC-MED) might be more attractive from the
23 point of view of the power plant operation since it is less dependent of the functioning
24 of the MED plant. Tables 6 and 7 show a comparison between the PT-CSP+LT-
25 MED+TVC and the PT-CSP+RO systems, considering dry cooling in both. In this case
26 the penalty in the power production is slightly larger than for Configuration #1 and, as
27 shown in Table 6, Configuration #2 is less efficient than #4 for all the *SEC* of both
28 desalination plants when the exhaust steam temperature is low (usual in the South of
29 Europe). However, the differences in the overall efficiency are small, decreasing with
30 increasing RO *SEC* and decreasing LT-MED *SEC* (they range from 13 % for 3.5
31 kWh/m³ to 7 % for 5.5 kWh/m³, considering 2.0 kWh/m³ for LT-MED *SEC*). In the
32 case of high exhaust steam temperature (MENA region) Configuration #2 is more
33 efficient thermodynamically than #4 from a RO *SEC* of 4.5 kWh/m³, regardless the *SEC*
34 of the LT-MED (see Table 7).
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40 Tables 8-9 show that when using evaporative water cooling as the refrigeration system,
41 Configuration #2 is more disadvantageous with respect to Configuration #4, and is more
42 efficient only in those places with high exhaust steam temperature (MENA region), high
43 *SEC* of the RO and low *SEC* of the MED.
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46 Finally, Tables 10 and 11 show the comparison between the configuration with RO and
47 the one with TVC-MED. In this case, it was obtained that the penalty in the power
48 production was even higher due to the fact that a higher amount of motive steam was
49 used in the ejector, so in all cases studied Configuration #4 was better in terms of
50 overall efficiency than Configuration #3. Only the results obtained for dry cooling are
51 shown as a representative example.
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54 5. Conclusions

55 Under certain conditions the integration of a MED unit into a PT-CSP plant is more
56 efficient than the independent fresh water and power production with a RO unit
57 connected to a PT-CSP plant. In the case of a LT-MED plant, it has been shown that its
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1 integration is more efficient than the combination of PT-CSP+RO when the exhaust
 2 steam leaves the turbine at high temperatures and the RO unit has high electric
 3 consumption (above 4.5 kWh/m³) for the three types of refrigeration systems. The
 4 integration of a TVC-MED into a PT-CSP plant has been observed to be less efficient
 5 than the system PT-CSP+RO in all the cases studied. However, the integration of a LT-
 6 MED+TVC is better and as a matter of fact has shown to be even more efficient than
 7 the system PT-CSP+RO in the case in which dry cooling is used as the refrigeration
 8 system when the temperature of the exhaust steam is high and the electric consumption
 9 of the RO unit is between 4.5 and 5.5 kWh/m³, which are conditions more likely to
 10 occur in the MENA region. Subsequently, in places where water consumption is a
 11 limiting factor and therefore dry cooling is preferred as the refrigeration system in the
 12 power plant, the integration of a LT-MED+TVC into a CSP, which avoids the
 13 operational problems of fully replacing the condenser of the power plant with a LT-
 14 MED, can be a feasible option. Also, it is important to highlight the saving in the
 15 cooling requirements of the power plant in the MED configuration with respect to the
 16 RO, as well as the higher technical needs that RO desalination has in comparison to
 17 MED, which does not require sophisticated pretreatment of seawater and needs less
 18 maintenance.
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22 **Nomenclature**

25	<i>CSP+D</i>	concentrating solar power and desalination
26	<i>DNI</i>	direct normal irradiance (kWh/m ² ·yr)
27	<i>EES</i>	Engineering Equation Solver
28	<i>GOR</i>	Gain Output Ratio
29	<i>LT-MED</i>	low temperature multi-effect distillation
30	<i>LT-MED-TVC</i>	low temperature multi-effect distillation powered by a thermal vapor 31 compressor
32	<i>TVC-MED</i>	thermal vapor compression multi-effect distillation
33	<i>RO</i>	reverse osmosis
34	<i>MENA</i>	Middle East and North Africa
35	<i>PT</i>	parabolic trough
36	<i>Cr</i>	pressure ratio
37	<i>Ra</i>	entrained ratio
38	<i>W</i>	power production, MWe
39	<i>m</i>	mass flow rate, kg/s
40	<i>h</i>	specific enthalpy, kJ/kg
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20 **Figure captions**

21 **Fig. 1.** Flow diagram of Configuration #1.

22 **Fig. 2.** Flow diagram of Configuration #2.

23 **Fig. 3.** Flow diagram of Configuration #3.

24 **Fig. 4.** Flow diagram of Configuration #4.

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Table 1

Operation conditions set for the thermodynamic simulation of the systems shown in Figs. 1-4

Point in the diagram	Parameters	Values
1	Temperature and Pressure	373 °C, 100 bar
2	Pressure	33.5 bar
3	Pressure	18.5 bar
4	Temperature and Pressure	373.4 °C, 16.5 bar
5	Pressure	14 bar
6	Pressure	6.18 bar
7	Pressure	3.04 bar
8	Pressure	1.17 bar ^a
9	Pressure	0.37 bar
11	Pressure	0.3121 bar
12	Pressure	0.1817 bar ^c
14	Pressure	8.38 bar
15	Pressure	103 bar

^a Vapor for the fourth extraction is used since the lower the motive steam pressure is, the lower the penalty in the overall efficiency of the power cycle is. A lower value would be very close to that one that is used to feed the LT-MED unit.

^c The entrained vapor is taken from an intermediate effect of the MED plant

Table 2

Overall efficiencies of the systems PT-CSP+LT-MED and PT-CSP+RO at an exhaust steam temperature of 37 °C considering dry cooling as the refrigeration method

<i>SEC</i> RO (kWh/m ³)											
3.5 4 4.5 5 5.5											
<i>SEC</i> LTMED (kWh/m ³)	LT MED	RO									
1.4	31.5	31.9	31.5	31.4	31.6	31.0	31.6	30.5	31.6	30.1	
1.6	31.3	31.9	31.3	31.4	31.3	30.9	31.3	30.5	31.3	30.0	
1.8	31.1	31.9	31.1	31.4	31.1	30.9	31.1	30.4	31.1	30.0	
2.0	30.9	31.8	30.9	31.3	30.9	30.9	30.9	30.4	30.9	30.0	
2.2	30.7	31.8	30.7	31.3	30.7	30.8	30.7	30.4	30.7	29.9	
2.4	30.5	31.8	30.5	31.3	30.5	30.8	30.5	30.3	30.54	29.9	

Table 3

Overall efficiencies of the systems PT-CSP+LT-MED and PT-CSP+RO at an exhaust steam temperature of 57 °C considering dry cooling as the refrigeration method

		<i>SEC</i> RO (kWh/m ³)									
		3.5		4		4.5		5		5.5	
<i>SEC</i> LT MED (kWh/m ³)		LT MED	RO	LT MED	RO	LT MED	RO	LT MED	RO	LT MED	RO
1.4		31.8	29.9	31.8	29.5	31.8	29.1	31.8	28.8	31.8	28.4
1.6		31.6	29.9	31.6	29.5	31.6	29.1	31.6	28.8	31.6	28.4
1.8		31.4	29.9	31.4	29.5	31.4	29.1	31.4	28.8	31.4	28.4
2.0		31.2	29.9	31.2	29.5	31.2	29.1	31.2	28.7	31.2	28.4
2.2		31.0	29.9	31.0	29.5	31.0	29.1	31.0	28.7	31.0	28.3
2.4		30.9	29.8	30.9	29.4	30.9	29.1	30.9	28.7	30.9	28.3

Table 4

Overall efficiencies of the systems PT-CSP+LT-MED and PT-CSP+RO at an exhaust steam temperature of 37 °C considering evaporative water cooling as the refrigeration method

		<i>SEC</i> RO (kWh/m ³)									
		3.5		4		4.5		5		5.5	
<i>SEC</i> LT MED (kWh/m ³)		LT MED	RO	LT MED	RO	LT MED	RO	LT MED	RO	LT MED	RO
1.4		31.5	33.5	31.5	32.9	31.5	32.4	31.5	31.9	31.5	31.3
1.6		31.3	33.4	31.3	32.9	31.3	32.3	31.3	31.8	31.3	31.3
1.8		31.1	33.4	31.1	32.9	31.1	32.3	31.1	31.8	31.1	31.3
2.0		30.9	33.4	30.9	32.8	30.9	32.3	30.9	31.8	30.9	31.2
2.2		30.7	33.4	30.7	32.8	30.7	32.3	30.7	31.7	30.7	31.2
2.4		30.5	33.3	30.5	32.8	30.5	32.2	30.5	31.7	30.5	31.2

Table 5

Overall efficiencies of the systems PT-CSP+LT-MED and PT-CSP+RO at an exhaust steam temperature of 57 °C considering evaporative water cooling as the refrigeration method

		<i>SEC</i> RO (kWh/m ³)									
		3.5		4		4.5		5		5.5	
<i>SEC</i> LTMED (kWh/m ³)		LT MED	RO	LT MED	RO	LT MED	RO	LT MED	RO	LT MED	RO
1.4		31.8	31.4	31.8	30.9	31.8	30.5	31.8	30.1	31.8	29.7
1.6		31.6	31.4	31.6	30.9	31.6	30.5	31.6	30.0	31.6	29.6
1.8		31.4	31.4	31.4	30.9	31.4	30.5	31.4	30.0	31.4	29.6
2.0		31.2	31.3	31.2	30.9	31.2	30.4	31.2	30.0	31.2	29.6
2.2		31.0	31.3	31.0	30.9	31.0	30.4	31.0	30.0	31.0	29.6
2.4		30.9	31.3	30.9	30.8	30.9	30.4	30.9	30.0	30.9	29.5

Table 6

Overall efficiencies of the systems PT-CSP+LT-MED+TVC and PT-CSP+RO at an exhaust steam temperature of 37 °C considering dry cooling as the refrigeration method

		<i>SEC</i> RO (kWh/m ³)									
		3.5		4		4.5		5		5.5	
<i>SEC</i> LTMED TVC (kWh/m ³)		LT MED TVC	RO	LT MED TVC	RO	LT MED TVC	RO	LT MED TVC	RO	LT MED TVC	RO
		1.4		28.7	31.9	28.7	31.4	28.7	31.0	28.7	30.5
1.6		28.5	31.9	28.5	31.4	28.5	30.9	28.5	30.5	28.5	30.0
1.8		28.3	31.9	28.3	31.4	28.3	30.9	28.3	30.4	28.3	30.0
2.0		28.1	31.8	28.1	31.3	28.1	30.9	28.1	30.4	28.1	30.0
2.2		27.9	31.8	27.9	31.3	27.9	30.8	27.9	30.4	27.9	29.9
2.4		27.7	31.8	27.7	31.3	27.7	30.8	27.7	30.3	27.7	29.9

Table 7

Overall efficiencies of the systems PT-CSP+LT-MED+TVC and PT-CSP+RO at an exhaust steam temperature of 57 °C considering dry cooling as the refrigeration method

		<i>SEC</i> RO (kWh/m ³)									
		3.5		4		4.5		5		5.5	
<i>SEC</i> LTMED TVC (kWh/m ³)		LT MED TVC	RO	LT MED TVC	RO	LT MED TVC	RO	LT MED TVC	RO	LT MED TVC	RO
		1.4		29.7	29.9	29.7	29.5	29.7	29.1	29.7	28.8
1.6		29.5	29.9	29.5	29.5	29.5	29.1	29.5	28.8	29.5	28.4
1.8		29.3	29.9	29.3	29.5	29.3	29.1	29.3	28.8	29.3	28.4
2.0		29.2	29.9	29.2	29.5	29.2	29.1	29.2	28.7	29.2	28.4
2.2		29.0	29.9	29.0	29.5	29.0	29.1	29.0	28.7	29.0	28.3
2.4		28.8	29.8	28.8	29.4	28.8	29.1	28.8	28.7	28.8	28.3

Table 8

Overall efficiencies of the systems PT-CSP+LT-MED+TVC and PT-CSP+RO at an exhaust steam temperature of 37 °C considering evaporative water cooling as the refrigeration method

		<i>SEC</i> RO (kWh/m ³)									
		3.5		4		4.5		5		5.5	
<i>SEC</i> LTMED TVC (kWh/m ³)		LT	RO	LT	RO	LT	RO	LT	RO	LT	RO
		MED TVC		MED TVC		MED TVC		MED TVC		MED TVC	
1.4		28.8	33.5	28.8	32.9	28.8	32.4	28.8	31.9	28.8	31.3
1.6		28.6	33.4	28.6	32.9	28.6	32.3	28.6	31.8	28.6	31.3
1.8		28.4	33.4	28.4	32.9	28.4	32.3	28.4	31.8	28.4	31.3
2.0		28.2	33.4	28.2	32.8	28.2	32.3	28.2	31.8	28.2	31.2
2.2		28.0	33.4	28.0	32.8	28.0	32.3	28.0	31.7	28.0	31.2
2.4		27.8	33.3	27.8	32.8	27.8	32.2	27.8	31.7	27.8	31.2

Table 9

Overall efficiencies of the systems PT-CSP+LT-MED+TVC and PT-CSP+RO at an exhaust steam temperature of 57 °C considering evaporative water cooling as the refrigeration method

		<i>SEC</i> RO (kWh/m ³)									
		3.5		4		4.5		5		5.5	
<i>SEC</i> LT MED TVC (kWh/m ³)		LT	RO	LT	RO	LT	RO	LT	RO	LT	RO
		MED TVC		MED TVC		MED TVC		MED TVC		MED TVC	
1.4		29.8	31.4	29.8	30.9	29.8	30.5	29.8	30.1	29.8	29.7
1.6		29.6	31.4	29.6	30.9	29.6	30.5	29.6	30.1	29.6	29.6
1.8		29.4	31.4	29.4	30.9	29.4	30.5	29.4	30.0	29.4	29.6
2.0		29.3	31.3	29.3	30.9	29.3	30.4	29.3	30.0	29.3	29.6
2.2		29.1	31.3	29.1	30.9	29.1	30.4	29.1	30.0	29.1	29.6
2.4		28.9	31.3	28.9	30.8	28.9	30.4	28.9	30.0	28.9	29.5

Table 10

Overall efficiencies of the systems PT-CSP+TVC-MED and PT-CSP+RO at an exhaust steam temperature of 37 °C considering dry cooling as the refrigeration method

		<i>SEC</i> RO (kWh/m ³)									
		3.5		4		4.5		5		5.5	
<i>SEC</i> TVC MED (kWh/m ³)		TVC MED	RO	TVC MED	RO	TVC MED	RO	TVC MED	RO	TVC MED	RO
1.2		27.6	31.9	27.6	31.4	27.6	31.0	27.6	30.5	27.6	30.1
1.4		27.4	31.9	27.4	31.4	27.4	31.0	27.4	30.5	27.4	30.1
1.6		27.2	31.9	27.2	31.4	27.2	30.9	27.2	30.5	27.2	30.0
1.8		27.0	31.9	27.0	31.4	27.0	30.9	27.0	30.4	27.0	30.0
2.0		26.8	31.8	26.8	31.3	26.8	30.9	26.8	30.4	26.8	30.0
2.2		26.6	31.8	26.6	31.3	26.6	30.8	26.6	30.4	26.6	29.9

Table 11

Overall efficiencies of the systems PT-CSP+TVC-MED and PT-CSP+RO at an exhaust steam temperature of 57 °C with dry cooling as refrigeration method

		<i>SEC</i> RO (kWh/m ³)									
		3.5		4		4.5		5		5.5	
<i>SEC</i> TVC MED (kWh/m ³)		TVC MED	RO	TVC MED	RO	TVC MED	RO	TVC MED	RO	TVC MED	RO
1.2		27.4	29.9	27.4	29.6	27.4	29.2	27.4	28.8	27.4	28.5
1.4		27.2	29.9	27.2	29.5	27.2	29.2	27.2	28.8	27.2	28.4
1.6		27.1	29.9	27.1	29.5	27.1	29.1	27.1	28.8	27.1	28.4
1.8		26.9	29.9	26.9	29.5	26.9	29.1	26.9	28.8	26.9	28.4
2.0		26.8	29.9	26.8	29.5	26.8	29.1	26.8	28.7	26.8	28.4
2.2		26.6	29.9	26.6	29.5	26.6	29.1	26.6	28.7	26.6	28.3